

Microwave assisted aminomethylation of some heterocyclic compounds bearing imidazolone moiety and their biological assay

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Abstract : Condensation of oxazolone with *p*-aminobenzoic acid furnished 4-(substituted benzylidene)-4,5-dihydro-2-phenyl-5-oxo-1*H*-imidazole-1-benzoic acid (1a-1c), which on subsequent cyclization with *o*-phenylene diamine yielded 4-(substituted benzylidene)-1-(1*H*-4,5-dihydrobenzimidazol-2-yl-1,4-phenylene)-2-phenyl-5-oxo-1*H*-imidazole (2a-2c). The compounds 2a-2c on heating with various amines and excess of paraformaldehyde in methanol led to Mannich bases (3a-3i). The synthesized compounds have been characterized on the basis of their elemental and spectral analyses. These compounds were evaluated for their antimicrobial activity against bacteria and fungi.

Keywords : Imidazolone, Mannich bases, microwave exposure.

Introduction

The growth of chemistry has been closely associated with the development of new bioactive molecules, which have been synthesized using newer and greener routes. Conventional methods of synthesis of chemical compounds with desired biological properties is time consuming and expensive, too. Thus, traditional medicinal chemistry remains the bottlenecks in the drug discovery processes. Consequently, there is an increased interest in technologies and concepts that facilitates more rapid synthesis and screening of chemical substances to identify compounds with appropriate qualities. One such high-speed technology is Microwave Assisted Organic Synthesis (MAOS). One fact that a "yes or no answer" for a particular chemical transformation can often be obtained within 5 to 10 min (as compared to several hours in conventional protocol) has contributed significantly to the acceptance of microwave chemistry both; in industry and academia^{1,2}. Therefore, in recent years, the acceleration of a wide range of chemical reactions using microwave dielectric heating has been reported³.

Imidazolones have been found to be associated with various biological activities such as potassium channel opener, phosphodiesterase III/IV inhibition and crop protection^{4,5}. Diverse biological activities such as anti-inflammatory⁶, antitubercular, antiviral and antifungal⁹ have been found to be associated with imidazolone derivatives. Recently, 1,2,4-trisubstituted-5-imidazolones have been reported to possess mono amino oxidase [MAO] inhibitory and anticonvulsant¹⁰ activities.

The aminomethylation reaction in presence of formaldehyde and secondary amines yields Mannich bases¹¹⁻¹³. A considerable amount of work has been reported on the synthesis and pharmacological activity of various Mannich bases for analgesic, antispasmodic, anesthetic and antimicrobial activity as well as intermediate in drug synthesis¹⁴⁻²⁵. Recently, Hassanein *et al.*²⁶ have reported the synthesis and biological evaluation of novel imidazolone derivatives as potential COX-2 inhibitors. It clearly demonstrates the remarkable potential of imidazolone derivatives and Mannich bases as a source of useful pharmacophore for new drug evolution.

In view of this, in present research work it was planned to apply MAOS technology to synthesize Mannich bases of some heterocyclic compounds bearing imidazolone moiety. This approach offers several advantages such as shorter reaction times, good yields and high purity of products. Moreover, its work up is simple and ecofriendly, too.

Results and discussion

Condensation of oxazolone with *p*-aminobenzoic acid furnished 4-(substituted benzylidene)-4,5-dihydro-2-phenyl-5-oxo-1*H*-imidazole-1-benzoic acid (**1a-1c**) under microwave irradiation. The structure of compounds **1a-1c** was confirmed by the IR bands at 3300 cm⁻¹ and 1560 cm⁻¹ due to -OH stretching of -COOH and C-N stretching, respectively. It is further supported by the presence of a broad singlet of OH proton in the region of 5.3 ppm in ¹H NMR. The compounds **1a-1c** were treated with *o*-phenylene diamine in the presence of HCl under microwave radiations to give 4-(substituted benzylidene)-1-(1*H*-4,5-dihydrobenzimidazol-2-yl)-1,4-phenylene)-2-phenyl-5-oxo-1*H*-imidazole (**2a-2c**). The structure of compounds **2a-2c** was confirmed by the disappearance of OH stretch in the region of 3300 cm⁻¹ in IR spectrum and appearance of an additional band at 3600 cm⁻¹ due to N-H stretching. ¹H NMR spectrum of compounds **2a-2c** show the appearance of a singlet due to one proton of NH at 9.3 ppm. The compounds **2a-2c** on heating with various amines and excess of paraformaldehyde in methanol lead to Mannich bases (**3a-3i**). The disappearance of signal in ¹H NMR spectrum and IR spectrum of compounds **3a-3i** due to N-H of imidazole ring confirm the installation of morpholine, *N*-methyl piperazine and *p*-chloroaniline moiety. In case of **3a**, another two couples of triplet appear around 3.6 and 2.9 ppm corresponding to the -CH₂-O-CH₂ and -CH₂-N-CH₂ groups, respectively. Similarly compound **3d** exhibits multiplet at 3.8 ppm indicating for 8 protons of piperazine ring. Compound **3g** has been confirmed by a multiplet at 8.4–7.6 ppm due to 21 aromatic protons. Compounds **3a-3i** exhibit singlet at around 4.0 ppm due to -CH₂-N group, which further confirms the structure of Mannich bases. Molecular ion peak [M]⁺ and other peaks appearing in mass spectra also confirm the structure of Mannich bases. Physical data of synthesized compounds are given in Table 1.

Compd.	Ar	Mol. formula	Mol. weight	M.p. (°C)	Yield (%)
1a	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ -OCH ₃	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₄	398	155	86
1b	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ -Cl	C ₂₃ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₃ Cl	402	182	81
1c	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ -F	C ₂₃ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₃ F	386	195	79
2a	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ -OCH ₃	C ₃₀ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₂	470	231	85
2b	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ -Cl	C ₂₉ H ₁₉ N ₄ OCl	474	216	78
2c	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ -F	C ₂₉ H ₁₉ N ₄ OF	458	225	73
3a	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ -OCH ₃	C ₃₅ H ₃₁ N ₅ O ₃	569	270	75
3b	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ -Cl	C ₃₄ H ₂₈ N ₅ O ₂ Cl	573	262	79
3c	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ -F	C ₃₄ H ₂₈ N ₅ O ₂ F	557	235	72
3d	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ -OCH ₃	C ₃₆ H ₃₄ N ₆ O ₂	582	241	69
3e	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ -Cl	C ₃₅ H ₃₁ N ₆ OCl	586	225	74
3f	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ -F	C ₃₅ H ₃₁ N ₆ OF	570	261	65
3g	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ -OCH ₃	C ₃₇ H ₂₈ N ₅ O ₂ Cl	609	252	71
3h	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ -Cl	C ₃₆ H ₂₅ N ₅ OCl ₂	613	236	77
3i	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ -F	C ₃₆ H ₂₅ N ₅ OClF	597	227	72

Antimicrobial activity :

Three compounds were screened *in vitro* for their antimicrobial activity against two strains of bacteria (*Proteus mirabilis* and *Bacillus subtilis*) and two strains of fungi (*Candida albicans* and *Aspergillus fumigatus*) using the disc diffusion method. Commercial antibacterial (Ciprofloxacin and Roxithromycin) and (antifungal Amphotericin-B and Fluconazole nondispersible) were also screened under similar conditions for comparison. The results have been reported in the form of inhibition zones and activity index in Table 2. The results revealed that all tested compounds except **3e** exhibited moderate to excel-

Table 2. The antimicrobial activities of some synthesized compounds at 500 ppm

Compd.	Zone of inhibition (mm) (Activity index)			
	Antibacterial activity		Antifungal activity	
	<i>P. mirabilis</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>	<i>A. fumigatus</i>
3c	18 (0.72)	23 (1.0)	17 (0.85)	13 (0.81)
3e	0.0 (0)	0.0 (0)	21 (1.05)	15 (0.94)
3g	16 (0.64)	5 (0.22)	19 (0.95)	17 (1.06)
Ciprofloxacin	25	23	-	-
Roxithromycin	10	8	-	-
Amphotericin-B	-	-	20	16
Fluconazole nondispersible	-	-	9	-

Activity index = Inhibition area of the sample/Inhibition area of the standard.

lent activity against both bacteria and strong activity against both fungi. However, compound **3e** did not show any activity on both bacterial strains.

Experimental

Apparatus :

All reactions were carried out in a domestic microwave oven (Kenstar, Model No. OM-26 EGO). Melting points are uncorrected and determined in open capillaries. Reactions were monitored by thin layer chromatography using silica gel-G as adsorbent. IR spectra (KBr pellets) were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 1800 spectrometer. ¹H NMR spectra were taken on a Bruker DRX FT NMR spectrometer (300 MHz) using TMS as internal standard and chemical shift were expressed in δ (ppm). Mass spectra were taken on a JEOL SX-102/PA-6000 (EI) spectrometer and elemental analysis was carried out on C, H, N analyzer (Elemental Vario Carlo Alba 1108). The results were found to be in good agreement with the calculated values (±0.2%).

Microwave assisted synthesis of 4-[(4E)-4-(4-methoxybenzylidene)-5-oxo-2-phenyl-4,5-dihydro-1H-imidazol-1-yl]benzoic acid (**1a**) :

A mixture of oxazolone (0.01 mol) and *p*-aminobenzoic acid (0.01 mol) in pyridine was heated in a domestic microwave oven in an open Erlenmeyer flask for 5.0 min. After cooling, the reaction mixture was poured into water. The solid thus obtained was filtered, dried and recrystallized from ethanol to yield compound **1a**. Found : C, 72.33; H, 4.49; N, 7.01. Calcd. for C₂₄H₁₈N₂O₄ : C, 72.36; H, 4.52; N, 7.03%; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3300 (OH str.), 3090 (C-H str., Ar-H), 2995, 2885 (asym. and sym. CH₃ str.), 1660 (C=O str.), 1625 (C=N str.), 1560 (C-N str.), 1180 (C-O str.), 816 (Ar bend., 1,4-disubstituted); ¹H NMR : δ (ppm) : 8.3-7.5 (13H, m, Ar-H), 5.9 (1H, s, exoolefinic =CH), 5.3 (1H, s, OH), 3.9 (3H, s, OCH₃).

4-[(4E)-4-(4-chlorobenzylidene)-5-oxo-2-phenyl-4,5-dihydro-1H-imidazol-1-yl]benzoic acid (**1b**) : Found : C, 68.62; H, 3.70; N, 6.94. Calcd. for C₂₃H₁₅N₂O₃Cl : C, 68.65; H, 3.73; N, 6.96%; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3290 (OH str.), 3075 (C-H str., Ar-H), 1655 (C=O str.), 1615 (C=N str.), 825 (Ar bend., 1,4-disubstituted), 725 (C-Cl str.); ¹H NMR : δ (ppm) : 8.6-7.1 (13H, m, Ar-H),

5.6 (1H, s, exoolefinic =CH), 5.1 (1H, s, OH).

4-[(4E)-4-(4-Fluorobenzylidene)-5-oxo-2-phenyl-4,5-dihydro-1H-imidazol-1-yl]benzoic acid (**1c**) : Found : C, 71.41; H, 3.85; N, 7.21. Calcd. for C₂₃H₁₅N₂O₃F : C, 71.50; H, 3.88; N, 7.25%; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3150 (OH str.), 3080 (C-H str., Ar-H), 1675 (C=O str.), 1620 (C=N str.), 1155 (C-F str.), 835 (Ar bend., 1,4-disubstituted); ¹H NMR : δ (ppm) : 8.9-7.8 (13H, m, Ar-H), 6.0 (1H, s, exoolefinic =CH), 5.4 (1H, s, OH).

Microwave induced synthesis of 4-(4-methoxybenzylidene)-1-(1H-4,5-dihydrobenzimidazol-2-yl-1,4-phenylene)-2-phenyl-5-oxo-1H-imidazole (**2a**) :

A mixture of compound **1a** (0.01 mol) and *o*-phenylene diamine (0.01 mol) in 4 N HCl was irradiated in MW for 3 min. The reaction mixture was neutralized with ammonia to give a solid, which on recrystallization from DMF gave compound **2a**. Found : C, 76.51; H, 4.62; N, 11.88. Calcd. for C₃₀H₂₂N₄O₂ : C, 76.59; H, 4.68; N, 11.91%; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3600 (N-H str.), 3100 (C-H str., Ar-H), 2890, 2895 (asym. and sym. -CH₃ str.), 1662 (C=O str.), 1635 (C=N str.), 817 (Ar bend., 1,4-disubstituted); ¹H NMR : δ (ppm) : 9.3 (1H, s, N-H), 7.5-8.3 (17H, m, Ar-H), 6.9 (1H, s, exoolefinic =CH), 4.4 (3H, s, OCH₃).

4-(4-Chlorobenzylidene)-1-(1H-4,5-dihydrobenzimidazol-2-yl-1,4-phenylene)-2-phenyl-5-oxo-1H-imidazole (**2b**) : Found : C, 73.38; H, 3.95; N, 11.78. Calcd. for C₂₉H₁₉N₄OCl : C, 73.41; H, 4.00; N, 11.81%; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3550 (N-H str.), 3080 (C-H str., Ar-H), 1640 (C=O str.), 1625 (C=N str.), 820 (Ar bend., 1,4-disubstituted), 755 (C-Cl str.); ¹H NMR : δ (ppm) : 9.0 (1H, s, N-H), 8.2-7.2 (17H, m, Ar-H), 6.8 (1H, s, exoolefinic =CH).

4-(4-Fluorobenzylidene)-1-(1H-4,5-dihydrobenzimidazol-2-yl-1,4-phenylene)-2-phenyl-5-oxo-1H-imidazole (**2c**) : Found : C, 75.93; H, 3.92; N, 14.76. Calcd. for C₂₉H₁₉N₄O₂F : C, 75.98; H, 4.00; N, 14.81%; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3610 (N-H str.), 3095 (C-H str., Ar-H), 1645 (C=O str.), 1637 (C=N str.), 1155 (C-F str.), 815 (Ar bend., 1,4-disubstituted); ¹H NMR : δ (ppm) : 9.5 (1H, s, N-H), 8.4-7.0 (17H, m, Ar-H), 6.0 (1H, s, exoolefinic =CH).

Microwave induced synthesis of 3{4-[1-(morpholine-4-yl-methyl)-1H-benzimidazole-2-yl]phenyl}-5-(4-

methoxybenzylidene-2-phenyl-3,5-dihydro-4H-imidazole-4-ones (**3a**): A solution of compound **2a** (0.01 mol), morpholine (0.01 mol) and paraformaldehyde (0.01 mol) in methanol (15.0 mL) was treated in microwave oven for 5–8 min. The separated solid was washed and recrystallized from methanol to give **3a**. Found: C, 73.79; H, 5.40; N, 12.25. Calcd. for $C_{35}H_{31}N_5O_3$: C, 73.81; H, 5.44; N, 12.30%; IR (KBr cm^{-1}): 3115 (C–H str., Ar–H), 2930 (C–H str., CH_2), 2890, 2800 (asym. and sym. $-CH_3$ str.), 1670 (C=O str.), 1625 (C=N str.), 1090 (C–O str.), 822 (Ar bend., 1,4-disubstituted); 1H NMR: δ (ppm): 8.3–7.5 (17H, m, Ar–H), 6.3 (1H, s, exoolefinic =CH), 4.4 (3H, s, OCH_3), 4.2 (2H, s, $-CH_2-N$), 3.60 (4H, t, CH_2-O-CH_2), 2.9 (4H, t, CH_2-N-CH_2); MS (m/z): 569, 462, 277, 262, 246, 216, 175, 170, 169, 116, 107, 100, 77.

3-{4-[1-(Morpholine-4-yl-methyl)-1H-benzimidazole-2-yl]phenyl}-5-(4-chlorobenzylidene)-2-phenyl-3,5-dihydro-4H-imidazole-4-ones (**3b**): Found: C, 71.18; H, 4.81; N, 12.19. Calcd. for $C_{34}H_{28}N_5O_2Cl$: C, 71.20; H, 4.88; N, 12.21%; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}): 3120 (C–H str., Ar–H), 2935 (C–H str., CH_2), 1645 (C=O str.), 1635 (C=N str.), 1110 (C–O str.), 815 (Ar bend., 1,4-disubstituted), 735 (C–Cl str.); 1H NMR: δ (ppm): 8.2–7.1 (17H, m, Ar–H), 6.5 (1H, s, exoolefinic =CH), 4.5 (2H, s, $-CH_2-N$), 3.8 (4H, t, CH_2-O-CH_2), 2.8 (4H, t, CH_2-N-CH_2); MS (m/z): 575, 573, 462, 281, 246, 216, 194, 170, 116, 111, 100, 77.

3-{4-[1-(Morpholine-4-yl-methyl)-1H-benzimidazole-2-yl]phenyl}-5-(4-fluorobenzylidene)-2-phenyl-3,5-dihydro-4H-imidazole-4-ones (**3c**): Found: C, 73.20; H, 4.9; N, 12.51. Calcd. for $C_{34}H_{28}N_5O_2F$: C, 73.24; H, 5.02; N, 12.56%; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}): 3095 (C–H str., Ar–H), 2980 (C–H str., CH_2), 2890, 1675 (C=O str.), 1615 (C=N str.), 1100 (C–O str.), 1155 (C–F str.), 820 (Ar–H bend., 1,4-disubstituted); 1H NMR: δ (ppm): 8.9–7.5 (17H, m, Ar–H), 6.7 (1H, s, exoolefinic =CH), 4.9 (2H, s, $-CH_2-N$), 3.5 (4H, t, CH_2-O-CH_2), 2.6 (4H, t, CH_2-N-CH_2); MS (m/z): 557, 462, 265, 246, 216, 178, 169, 116, 100, 77.

3-{4-[1-(N-Methylpiperazine-4-yl-methyl)-1H-benzimidazole-2-yl]phenyl}-5-(4-methoxybenzylidene)-2-phenyl-3,5-dihydro-4H-imidazole-4-ones (**3d**): Found: C, 74.19; H, 5.82; N, 14.10. Calcd. for $C_{36}H_{34}N_6O_2$: C, 74.22;

H, 5.84; N, 14.40%; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}): 3100 (C–H str., Ar–H), 2926 (C–H str., CH_2), 2895, 2800 (asym. and sym. $-CH_3$ str.), 1650 (C=O str.), 1625 (C=N str.), 1105 (C–O str.), 816 (Ar bend., 1,4-disubstituted); 1H NMR: δ (ppm): 8.3–7.0 (17H, m, Ar–H), 6.3 (1H, s, exoolefinic =CH), 4.5 (3H, s, OCH_3), 4.0 (2H, s, $-CH_2-N$), 3.8 (8H, m, $(-CH_2-N)_4$), 1.8 (3H, s, CH_3); MS (m/z): 582, 475, 277, 225, 214, 200, 198, 170, 130, 113, 107, 77.

3-{4-[1-(N-Methylpiperazine-4-yl-methyl)-1H-benzimidazole-2-yl]phenyl}-5-(4-chlorobenzylidene)-2-phenyl-3,5-dihydro-4H-imidazole-4-ones (**3e**): Found: C, 71.64; H, 5.21; N, 14.28. Calcd. for $C_{35}H_{31}N_6OCl$: C, 71.67; H, 5.29; N, 14.33%; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}): 3095 (C–H str., Ar–H), 2940 (C–H str., CH_2), 2895, 2860 (asym. and sym. $-CH_3$ str.), 1635 (C=O str.), 1610 (C=N str.), 820 (Ar–H bend., 1,4-disubstituted), 750 (C–Cl str.); 1H NMR: δ (ppm): 8.1–7.6 (17H, m, Ar–H), 6.2 (1H, s, exoolefinic =CH), 4.2 (2H, s, $-CH_2-N$), 3.9 (8H, m, $(-CH_2-N)_4$), 2.3 (3H, s, CH_3); MS (m/z): 588, 586, 475, 281, 229, 214, 204, 202, 170, 130, 113, 107, 77.

3-{4-[1-(N-Methylpiperazine-4-yl-methyl)-1H-benzimidazole-2-yl]phenyl}-5-(4-fluorobenzylidene)-2-phenyl-3,5-dihydro-4H-imidazole-4-ones (**3f**): Found: C, 73.61; H, 5.40; N, 14.70. Calcd. for $C_{35}H_{31}N_6OF$: C, 73.68; H, 5.43; N, 14.73%; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}): 3080 (C–H str., Ar–H), 2955 (C–H str., CH_2), 2895, 2880 (asym. and sym. $-CH_3$ str.), 1655 (C=O str.), 1640 (C=N str.), 1110 (C–F str.), 825 (Ar–H bend., 1,4-disubstituted); 1H NMR: δ (ppm): 8.6–7.8 (17H, m, Ar–H), 5.7 (1H, s, exoolefinic =CH), 4.7 (2H, s, $-CH_2-N$), 4.0 (8H, m, $(-CH_2-N)_4$), 2.5 (3H, s, CH_3); MS (m/z): 570, 475, 265, 213, 188, 170, 120, 113, 107, 77.

3-{4-[1-(4-Chlorophenyl)amino-methyl]-1H-benzimidazole-2-yl]phenyl}-5-(4-methoxybenzylidene)-2-phenyl-3,5-dihydro-4H-imidazole-4-ones (**3g**): Found: C, 72.87; H, 4.54; N, 11.45. Calcd. for $C_{37}H_{28}N_5O_2Cl$: C, 72.90; H, 4.59; N, 11.49%; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}): 3165 (N–H str.), 3100 (C–H str., Ar–H), 2980, 2875 (asym. and sym. $-CH_3$ str.), 1655 (C=O str.), 1638 (C=N str.), 1105 (C–O str.), 816 (Ar–H bend., 1,4-disubstituted), 715 (C–Cl str.); 1H NMR: δ (ppm): 8.4–7.6 (21H, m, Ar–H), 6.2 (1H, s, NH), 5.8 (1H, s, exoolefinic =CH), 4.4 (2H, s, $-CH_2-N$), 4.1 (3H, s, OCH_3); MS (m/z): 611, 609, 502,

225, 200, 170, 140, 126, 116, 107, 77.

3-{4-[1-{(4-Chlorophenyl)amino-methyl}-1H-benzimidazole-2-yl]phenyl}-5-(4-chlorobenzylidene)-2-phenyl-3,5-dihydro-4H-imidazole-4-ones (**3h**): Found: C, 70.43; H, 4.03; N, 11.38. Calcd. for C₃₆H₂₅N₅OCl₂: C, 70.47; H, 4.07; N, 11.41%; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹): 3350 (N-H str.), 3025 (C-H str., Ar-H), 1645 (C=O str.), 1625 (C=N str.), 835 (Ar-H bend., 1,4-disubstituted), 720 (C-Cl str.); ¹H NMR: δ (ppm): 8.9-7.4 (21H, m, Ar-H), 6.0 (1H, s, exoolefinic =CH), 5.6 (1H, s, NH), 4.9 (2H, s, -CH₂-N); MS (m/z): 615, 613, 502, 229, 204, 170, 143, 130, 136, 111, 77.

3-{4-[1-{(4-Chlorophenyl)amino-methyl}-1H-benzimidazole-2-yl]phenyl}-5-(4-fluorobenzylidene)-2-phenyl-3,5-dihydro-4H-imidazole-4-ones (**3i**): Found: C, 72.32; H, 4.15; N, 11.69. Calcd. for C₃₆H₂₅N₅OClF: C, 72.36; H, 4.18; N, 11.72%; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹): 3225 (N-H str.), 3080 (C-H str., Ar-H), 1675 (C=O str.), 1615 (C-N str.), 1160 (C-F str.), 824 (Ar-H bend.), 735 (C-Cl str.); ¹H NMR: δ (ppm): 8.2-7.9 (21H, m, Ar-H), 6.5 (1H, s, NH), 5.4 (1H, s, exoolefinic =CH), 4.9 (2H, s, -CH₂-N); MS (m/z): 599, 597, 502, 213, 188, 170, 140, 130, 116, 95, 77.

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